

The Role of Tribal Communities in Achieving Viksit Bharat 2047

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19158592>

Abstract:

Tribal Communities are different from other citizens by demographic, cultural, political, ecological, and ethical environment. It co-relates the role of Tribal Communities in Achieving Viksit Bharat 2047. This research paper mainly focuses on Forest and wildlife conservation, sustainable agricultural practices, holistic medical practices, fort heritage conservation, and contribution in economic development, Contribution in Tourism Industry and Environmental contribution. This also co-relates role of tribal communities in achieving Sustainable Development Goals as determined by United Nations Organization in the year 2015. Viksit Bharat stage can be achieved by focusing on four pillars i.e. Garib, Yuva, Nari & Annadata (Poor, Youth, Women and Farmers). This research paper tries how contribution of Tribals is important in achieving vision and mission of Viksit Bharat by 2047.

Keywords - Tribal, Communities, Viksit, Bharat, Four Pillars - GYAN (Garib, Youth, Annadata, Nari), Sustainable Development Goals, Sustainable Agricultural Practices, Cultural Heritage Conservation,

Introduction

‘Viksit Bharat’ means ‘Developed India’ Viksit Bharat is a Vision of Government of India to drive the mission of making India a fully developed rashtra (Nation) by its 100th Anniversary of Independence in the year 2047. India got Independence from British rules after fight of 100 years (from Kranti of 1857 to Independence 1947). However, India is in developing stage in various aspects such as Education, Healthcare, Agricultural, Industrial & Infrastructural, Women Empowerment, Space research, National security etc. The vision is based on GYAN concepts- Garib (Poors), Yuva (Youth), Annadata (Farmers) and Nari (Women).

Tribal Communities (Adivasi / Adibasi) are the heterogeneous tribal groups across the Indian subcontinent. The term *Adivasi*, a 20th-century construct meaning "ancient inhabitants", is now widely used as a self-designation by many of the communities who are officially recognized as "Scheduled Tribes" in India¹ (wikepeia.org) The total scheduled tribe population was 10.43 crore representing 8.6 % of the country's total population. Out of 1.04

crore resided in urban areas, with the majority located in forest and hilly regions. (Department, 2011) (Census of India -2011)ⁱⁱ Madhya Pradesh is First ST Population (15.30 million) while Maharashtra State is at 2nd position (10.5 million). Tribal community comprises more than 700 tribes, but in Maharashtra total 47 tribes include Bhil, Gond, Santhal, Munda, Katkari, Thakkar, Korku, Koya, Pawara, Kolam, Kotiya, Pardhi, Madiya, Varli, Kathodi Vitola etc resides in Hilly Regions.

Sustainable Development Goals as 17 Global objectives adopted by UNO in 2015, focuses on No Poverty, Zero Hunger, Good Health, Quality Education, Gender Equality, Affordable and Clean Energy, Life of Land, Responsible Consumption and Productions etc can be achieved by every country. Indian Tribal Communities working on some of these goals from Ancient period.

Objectives

1. To analyze the Vision and Mission of Viksit Bharat -2047.
2. To study sustainable development Goals given by United Nations
3. To study holistic role of Tribal Communities engaged in achieving goals of Viksit Bharat.
4. To study contribution and importance of Tribals in achieving SDG

Scope

1. In this research paper, researcher tried to find out role of Tribal communities from ancient period.
2. This paper takes into consideration local practices implemented by Tribal Communities especially of Akole Tehsil of Ahilyanagar District which contributes in achieving Viksit Bharat 2047.

Methodology

This research paper is based on secondary data, information available on government websites, Ancient Texts, Published newspaper articles. Also based on primary sources used for information collection such as field visit, observation and interviews taken from Tribal communities in the October 2025, especially from Tribal (Adivasi) region i.e. Akole Tehsil of Ahilyanagar District of Maharashtra.

Important Terms:

1. Adivasi:

The Adivasi is derived from the Sanskrit words *Adi* (beginning / earliest time) and *Vasi* (dweller/resident). It literally translates to "**original inhabitants**" or "**indigenous people**".

2. Tribe:

Tribes refers to the group or community of people that have same language and customs culture, often living in a specific area and organised by kinship, traditions or a common leader.

Key Pillars of Viksit Bharat 2047ⁱⁱⁱ

Viksit Bharat 2047 is a comprehensive master plan to transform India into a developed nation by the 100th anniversary of its independence. The four key pillars of Viksit Bharat are Garib (Poor), Yuva (Youth), Nari (Women) and Annadata (Farmers). Let's take a look at the key pillars of Viksit Bharat 2047: -

1. Garib (Poor)

The Viksit Bharat 2047 government aims for zero poverty in India through inclusive development and financial empowerment. It ensures 100% saturation of basic amenities such as housing, electricity and water. Also, AI tools are making specialized healthcare more accessible and affordable for the poor, while AI educational tools are reducing linguistic and geographic barriers to provide quality learning.

2. Yuva (Youth)

Viksit Bharat 2047 aims at empowering young people who are known as 'Yuva' through skill development and education to drive the future economy of the country. Platforms like My Bharat uplifts the youth through innovation led growth, skill building and volunteering opportunities.

3. Nari (Women)

Viksit Bharat 2047 aims at women-led development and increasing their economic participation to 70% by 2027. Over 28 crore women have already opened the Jan Dhan accounts and the majority of beneficiaries under the PM Mudra Yojana and Stand-Up India are women.

4. Annadata (Farmers)

Annadata segment of the Viksit Bharat 2047 aims at modernizing agriculture to make India the food basket of the world. The primary goal is to increase the average farmer's income by up to five times current levels through better market access.

Role of Tribal Communities in Viksit Bharat By 2047:

Government of India through his Viksit Bharat Documents shows that number of steps were taken for eradication poverty to zero, Farmers Welfare, Education, Women empowerment, Infrastructural Development, support for MSME and Startups, PM Awas Yojana, PM Jand Dhan Basic Saving Accounts scheme, Ayushman Bharat Healthcare, Gobardhan Scheme, Kusum Solar Electrification for Farmers, Pradhan Mantri Gramin Digital Saksharta Abhiyan etc

Following points shows actual roles of Tribal Communities in Vikshit Bharat Mission 2047.

- 1. Sustainable Agricultural Practices:** Tribal communities' worldwide employed time based sustainable agricultural practices that prioritize ecological balance, biodiversity, resources conservation. They implement Mixed and Diversified Cropping, Agroforestry, organic Soil Management. These methods often rooted in Bhartiya Jyan Parampara, minimize external inputs and ensuring long term soil health and food security. The Major Crops cultivated by tribes of the selected sample are rice in rainy season and other Vegetables in early days of summer. Tribes used their indigenous seeds conserved by their family. **Sau. Rahibai Popere is received Padmashri Award for their contribution of conserving indigenous seeds.** She is also called as Beej Mata (Mother of Indigenous Seeds). Tribal's every household have Indian Godhan (Cows), milk from such cows and buffalo's is used for regular use and also sold for further process. Cow dung and Urine of Cows used for farming as fertilizers. Farmers also use Oxes for regular farming activities. They have use Bio fertilizers and bio chemicals (such as Slury, Vermiwash etc) for crops. It reduces dependency of external inputs, chemical fertilizers, pesticides etc.
- 2. Holistic Medicinal Practices:** Tribal communities worldwide employ sustainable medical practices deeply rooted in traditional ecological knowledge. These methods harmonize with nature. In research sample area communities used plants, herbs-based medicine for primary treatment. For example, Ashwagandha, Tulsi, Adulasa, Cow urines etc. They also take care of herbs and conserve them. These approaches protect native plants species during collection, they reduce dependence on imported drugs, making healthcare affordable and accessible in remote areas. However, e Sanhjeevani OPD and PM Jan Aushadi Yojana also available in remote area.
- 3. Protection of Forest and Wildlife:** Tribal communities act as vital guardians of forests and wildlife by employing sustainable, traditional practices rooted in ecological wisdom. They conserve biodiversity through sacred groves, rotational farming and regulated harvesting. Their deep spiritual connection with nature ensures the protection to wildlife (prohibiting hunting) and reforestation, sustainable resource usage (harvesting of herbs,

honey, firewood's). They are not polluting environment, as they don't use modern polluting materials such as plastic, glass materials, heavy metals, chemical-based fertilizers. Tribal play a major role in fighting forest fire.

4. **Fort Heritage Conservation:** Tribal communities play a vital role in the conservation of fort heritage, primarily by serving as traditional custodians of the surrounding ecosystems, acting as guardians of the structures, and integrating their cultural knowledge into preservation efforts. Tribal Communities involvement ensures the protection of both tangible (the fort Structure) and Intangible (natural Surroundings, history) heritage. They often manage forests surrounding forts, preventing illegal logging and encroachment, which indirectly protects the fort's natural setting. They also protect natural water bodies, streams and tanks within and around fort. They manage vegetations and prevent forest fires that can damage nearby historical sites. In sample area there are many forts available in Sahyadri rang and Tribal area. This structure reflects Maratha Era Architecture and strategic hilltop location. **There eight forts that is Vishramgad (Patta Killa), Aad Fort, Harishchandra Gadh, Ratangadh Fort, Aajobagadh, Pabargadh, Madangadh and Bitangadh.** (Maharashtra)
5. **Contribution in Tourism Industry:** Akole Tehsil areas Natural Attractions and Cultural Significance play major contribution in tourism industry. Features of Sahyadri mountain range including Kalsubai Peak, Harishchandra Gadh, Konkan Kada, Sandan Valley, Randha and Umrella Waterfalls, Wilson Dam, Jagdamba Mandir, Amruteshwar Temple - Kajava Mahotstav, birds watching, Wildlife safaris, eco- tourism, boating in Willson Dam etc contributed in tourism. Home of Tribal communities like Mahadev Koli, Takkar offers cultural tourism through festivals, traditions (Shri. Sakharam Thaka Gangadh and his team belongs to Thakkar represent their community in cultural events preserving traditions)
6. **Contribution in Economic Development:** The Van Dhan Yojana a component of the 'Mechanism for Marketing of Minor Forest Produce (MFP) through Minimum Support Price (MSP) & Development of Value Chain for MFP' was launched on 14th April, 2018. Implemented by TRIFED as the nodal agency at the national level, the Van Dhan Start-ups is a well thought master plan for the socio-economic development of the tribal population of the country^{iv}. In 2025, the Pradhan Mantri Van Dhan Yojana (PMVDY) continues to generate revenue by transforming tribal, forest-dwelling communities from mere primary collectors of Minor Forest Produce (MFP) into entrepreneurs through value addition, processing, and branding. As a mid of 2025-26, over 4661 Van Dhan Vikas

Kendra's have been sanctioned, associating 12.80 lakh beneficiaries and generation combined sales of ₹ 129.86 crore (approx.) (PMVVY, 2025). (Retail outlets of Maharashtra State is Pune Mahila Mandal, 17, Parrvati Payatha Pune 411009.) Such PMVDY helps to Tribal SHGs value addition increases the income of tribal gathers by 40—60 %. Key Products includes Honey, Mahua, Tamarind, Clustered Apples and Bamboo.

Finding:

Taking into consideration various data and information available at various primary and secondary sources researchers finding are as:

1. India is in developing stage – nearby 70 percent population still living in Villages, supporting agricultural activities and tribal economies. Raw materials available from these sectors are important in development of Industry and Economic and overall development.
2. Tribal Communities use various eco-friendly and less harmful techniques in agricultural sectors, that will valuable in achieving Viksit Bharat. They rarely use chemicals fertilizers, pesticides in agriculture.
3. The contribution of Tribals in Economic development is more of qualitative and sustainable rather than quantitative.
4. Development also signifies individual advancement in skill building and use of sustainable practices, traditions, handicrafts which is least harmful to environment.
5. Tribal Communities conserves bio-diversity, protect environment that contribute sustainable human – environment development.

Suggestions:

1. Tribals engaged in farming activity will be given support to sell their products at national and international market.
2. Tribals should be given more support from government in terms of Loans, Technology, marketing support etc.
3. Tribals have knowledge of Ayurveda, medicine hence to preserve and to bring it to the international level, research should be made in their practices and indigenous knowledge
4. Government should provide funds and allotment of heritage conservation in nearby area of Tribal communities.
5. Financial Support to develop tourism places should be given by the government to the Tribal's in Ahilyanagar District.
6. Folk dance institutes should be created and funded to develop the skills of Adivasi.

Conclusions

Viksit Bharat 2047 is Government of India's vision to transform the nation into a fully developed, self-reliant and prosperous country by 2047. It aims at ensuring high living standards, quality education and healthcare for citizens of the country. It also wants to eliminate poverty by increasing economic growth by targeting a trillion economy, social advancement, infrastructure, sustainability and robust governance. It aims for zero poverty, high per capital income and AI driven development. Desired Stage of Viksit Bharat can be achieved by 2047 with the development of Youth, Women's and Farmers. When three elements i.e. Mind- Brain – Hands comes together for constructive goals of development, and when we inspired and inculcate principles of “वसुधैव कुटुम्बकम्” by the Ethical and Sustainable practices in all activities, then we definitely achieve goals of Viksit Bharat. India 's G-20 theme “One Earth, One Family, One Future” applies this to economic policies, emphasizing shared prosperity over competition. It aligns with tribal communities' economic empowerment integrating Indigenous Traditional Knowledge into mainstream markets for Holistic Development.

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